

Prevalence of Students with Specific Learning Disabilities at Primary Level: A Case of Province of Punjab

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 15, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Specific Learning Disabilities, Factors Affecting, Teacher Planning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6355293</p>	<p><i>Specific learning disparities are like a termite to any society which needs particular concentration. Students with specific learning disabilities may suffer in Speaking, reading, writing, and mathematics. The objective of this study was to figure out the Prevalence of Students with Specific Learning Disabilities at Primary Level in Punjab. The study population was children studying in the primary schools of Punjab. The data was collected from 2392 children. WIAT-III test was used for data collection from the students. It comprised Oral Language, Total Reading, Basic Reading, Reading Comprehension and Fluency, Written Expression, Mathematics, Math Fluency tests. The results show that 50% of children have learning disabilities in different areas as discussed in the paper withy detail. It is recommended that Special support services must be established to provide the necessary provision, and regular in-service trainings for the management and teachers should be arranged at their schools for awareness.</i></p>

Introduction

Specific learning disabilities impact badly at the life of children. Students with Specific Learning disabilities have difficulty in speaking, writing, reading, and mathematic abilities. Causes include disorders of the central nervous system. In combination with other impairments (e.g., visual or auditory impairment, mental retardation and social/emotional problems), specific learning difficulties might arise. These conditions and effects are not the direct outcome. Variables like cultural disparities, improper and inadequate education and psychogenic factors, among others, are also responsible for them (Ismail, Mohamed & Soltan, 2019; Aftab, 2018). While it seems normal, many children do not perform because of a psychological issue at their age and skill level. Due to these psychological problems, there is a difference between the child's performance and his oral and listening intellectual skills. In other words, learning disabled children are not very successful (Wigfield et al., 2004).

As defined by the American Psychiatric Association (APA), reading, writing, and mathematical disabilities are classified as dyslexia, dysgraphia, and dyscalculia, respectively. The most common form of LD is reading disability, which affects 70 to 80 percent of students. For these students reading comprehension, speech speed, decoding, and word recognition are all difficult tasks. In addition, they have problems with letter combinations and phonemic awareness. Early detection affects the future of a child considerably, making instructors a key factor in early identification and giving families with proper assistance. Adequate understanding about particular learning impairment should be provided for primary trainees (Karande, Bhosrekar, Kulkarni & Thakker, 2009).

Learning disabilities are very common and hidden in the children. Parents do not pay attention for LD in children specially at primary level. In Pakistan, there is a lack of research on learning disabilities in primary school students. At the primary level, there is a great need to investigate learning disabilities. The purpose of this study is to uncover the truth about this issue.

Objective of Research

To explore the prevalence of specific learning disabilities (SLDs) among primary school children in Punjab.

Literature Review

The consequences of specific learning disabilities are profound for the children. It remains with them throughout their lives and impacts badly on the life of children for their success at each step of life. Related literature regarding the specific learning disparities is explored to figure out the detail of these learning disabilities. This study is unique due to examining the prevalence of LD in Pakistan as there was very little research conducted on this topic earlier.

Definition of Learning Disabilities:

Speaking, writing, reading and mathematical ability is challenging to certain students with learning disabilities. As with other disabilities (e.g., mental impairment, social and emotional disorders), learning disabilities do not come directly from such other disability or effects (e.g., culture, inadequate and psychogenic factors). Kirk & Crallagher (1979) brought learning disabilities to a group of parents and professionals concerned. Children with comparable school disabilities were reported to have modest mental delays, little malfunction in the brain, dyslexia, impaired perception, neurological impairment and slow learners until recently. Many of these problems are now known in the US as learning disabilities. The nature and frequency of different learning problems/disabilities (LD) has been investigated during school psychology in the past several years in elementary school student (Gebhardt, Zehner, & Hesselsb, 2014).

Reading, writing, speaking, thinking, listening, and mathematical calculations are all affected by learning difficulty/disability (LD). Disabilities such as mental retardation, emotional disturbances, and visual/auditory impairments are excluded from this list (Individual with Disability Education Act, 2004). The symptoms of Specific learning disabilities (LDs) can take many forms and include difficulties with reading, writing, and mathematics, observed in students (Aftab, 2018; Barbaresi et al., 2005).

A report by the American Psychiatric Association (2016) categorizes reading disorders (dyslexia), writing disorders (dysgraphia), and math disabilities (dyscalculia). The most common form of LD is reading disability, which affects 70 to 80 percent of students. Their reading comprehension, speech rate, comprehension, and word recognition are all disabilities. As a result of this, they have difficulty in matching letter combinations and recognizing phonetic sounds. However, a writing disability is characterized by problems with written expression, punctuation, and grammar. Mathematical disability, on the other hand, is less known. Despite being under-investigated, a lot of work has been done in identifying math deficits, with about 7 percent of students having such problems (Barbaresi et al., 2005; Shalev et al., 2008).

Many people use the terms mathematical deficits, math disability, and dyscalculia interchangeably when referring to mathematical disability (Geary, Hoard, Nugent & Bailey, 2008). Specific learning ideas, equations, values, numbers organization, recalling mathematical information and comprehending how issues are handled with this type of LD are challenging (Aftab, 2018; APA, 2013).

Common symptoms of learning disabilities:

Learning disability symptoms are most often every day. At some stages, any of these symptoms might be severe. These include dyscalculia (issues with mathematical operations), dysgraphia (handwriting problems), information processing disorders, linguist-related problems or age-appropriate verbal or written communication problems (inability to properly utilize sensory information), dyslexia and significant developmental delay when other areas are typical or beyond average (Alone & Bamnote, 2020).

Degree of Learning Disabilities:

There are varying degrees of learning disabilities, which is why they were categorized according to their severity (Adima, 1992);

(i) Mild learning disabilities: Even though this is not considered a severe issue, it is tough enough to draw the attention of parents and educators. It is possible to integrate learners with mild LD successfully. Into a general education classroom where the public and special educationists will share the delivery of education services. As a result, if this condition is ignored, it may worsen (Adima, 1992).

(ii) Moderate learning disabilities: For the child to be successful, they need intensive assistance. In a resource room, learners with moderate LD Need remedial instruction to learn. The resource room allows students to receive specialized education while remaining part of the school community. As well as being able to customize the program for each student, the resource rooms have a variety of materials (Adima, 1992).

(iii) Severe learning disabilities: At this level, the child cannot learn without unique materials, unique methods, and an individually tailored educational program (IEP). These students require intensive and comprehensive intervention in a separate class or a particular school, as this is a severe condition. It appears that these students have a better self-concept in a separate class than they do in a regular classroom. Since fewer teachers per student here, the learning environment is more intensive, allowing students to spend more time learning and making more progress in academic and social areas. One or more of these classifications may be used by teachers in the classroom at some point. These classifications will help teachers determine whether or not a student has LD and the severity of their learning difficulties (Smith, 1991).

Learning Disabilities across Genders at primary level:

LDs seem to be more frequent among boys of school age than among girls of school age. It is believed that almost two thirds of children of school age with learning impairments are boys. Learning disability (LD) research stated that males in the school population with LD were above the number of girls by a ratio of 5:1 to 9:1 and not only a little. According to IDEA, two thirds of children with a "specific learning handicap" are male. As a result, children have more than double the risk of ADHD diagnosis as females. Boys are more likely to be diagnosed than females when it comes to learning and attention problems. A recent, comprehensive study found an equally large number of boys and girls with learning disabilities. More boys than girls are officially

diagnosed with learning disabilities and ADHD, so it seems that way. As far as learning and behavioral problems go, LD and ADHD are the two most common diagnoses in schools today (Reynolds, Pietrzak, El-Gabalawy, Mackenzie & Sareen, 2015). When it comes to cognitive developmental disorders in childhood, boys are more susceptible than girls. A variation in the etiology of learning disabilities and disparities in learning styles between children and girls can explain the prevalence in learning difficulties in males (Nass, 1993).

There was no gender discrepancy in well-known research of 400 students when it comes to learning challenges. But this was not subjective but based on scientific standards. Teachers suggested the LD programs to twice as many boys when calling. Maybe it's because females and guys behave differently. We all know that boys tend to draw more unfavorable attention in school than their females. Research shows that guys account for 85% of all punishment references. Another research revealed that 22% of boys and just 8% of girls were punished (Fletcher, Lyon, Barnes, Stuebing, Francis, Olson & Shaywitz, 2002).

Research suggests that ADHD males likely to be hyperactive, impulsive and physically violent rather than ADHD boys. They stand out from the rest of the boys because of their behavior. Males with ADHD tend to be more noticeable than females. And that may explain why they are diagnosed with the disorder more than twice as frequently. We don't know if boys are more prone to learning and attention problems than females. However, we know that when children are identified, they are more likely to receive the best possible care and assistance. As a result, many girls are not getting the help they need because they are not identified. Families with struggling daughters may need to be even more aggressive in advocating for their children. However, it's important to note that temperament plays a significant role in a child's personality. In terms of motor activity, boys tend to be more active than girls (Mayes, Calhoun & Crowell, 2000).

Characteristics of Learning Disabilities:

When it comes to Specific learning disabilities, many different symptoms are associated with the condition. Among the top ten most frequently cited characteristics are (Devshi et al., 2015);

- (i) Hyperactivity:** A hyperactive child runs a long time and cannot sit still and perform tasks without thinking.
- (ii) Perceptual-motor impairments:** Inadequate coordination with a motor act of visual or aural input.
- (iii) Emotional lability:** Emotional eruptions that observers find unjustifiable in light of current circumstances or a child's recent experience. Often, these emotional ups and downs can be traced back to a specific cause. An unsatisfactory job performance, a looming bill or deadline, or a lack of sleep the night before are all possible causes (Devshi et al., 2015).
- (iv) General coordination deficits:** Timidity or hesitancy. A child with an educational impairment might have difficulties, such as cutting, buttoning, lacing, copying from a crayon board and sorting things in accordance with their forms and sizes.
- (v) Disorder of attention: either distractibility** - Concentrate on something too long or give attention to what you shouldn't (Devshi et al., 2015).
- (vi) Impulsivity:** without serious thought and thought.
- (vii) Disorder of memory** or thinking, the incapacity to understand abstract concepts and to retain the content learned: A child may also be unable to maintain the sounds, words or letters he has learnt with specific requirements. It also impairs understanding ability. For example, instead of tops, a child may write stops.
- (viii) Specific learning disabilities:** Could not learn to read, spell, write, understand, and calculate arithmetic (Devshi et al., 2015).
- (ix) Disorders in speech and hearing:** Articulation deficiencies, problems with verbal expressions and with the right words.
- (x) Equivocal neurological signs:** A child with a learning impairment might suffer brain damage as behavioral symptoms, for example, loss of fine motor coordination, timidity and slurred speech (Devshi et al., 2015).

But it's important to remember that not every child with a learning disability has all of these issues. And having one of them does not imply that a child is learning-impaired by default. In programmed for learning disabilities, the majority of children show signs of learning difficulties. The characteristics of L.D. can be determined once they are identified. Educators must understand the classification of L.D. to place students appropriately (Devshi et al., 2015).

Prevalence of learning disabilities:

Disabilities in Learning are the result of an abnormality in the brain's operating systems. So, the brain takes in and processes certain types of information uniquely and unusually, making it challenging to reach typical learning milestones. Genetic factors may influence the development of learning disabilities in many cases. Supervision, poor eyesight, birth trauma, or neurological damage to the womb can produce alterations in the brain as well as social and environmental deprivation. Children with chronic illness suffer learning impairments twice as often as children with chronic illnesses. Those receiving special schooling are more likely than children who do not to seek medical treatment. Inherent reasons such as poor eyesight, soreness and environmental variables can be correctable or improved by some developmental difficulties (Cummings, 2013).

Risk factors for learning disabilities:

Many variables raise the chance of a child becoming disabled with learning. There is no assurance of a learning problem for all persons with risk factors. A multitude of circumstances, including alcohol or adverse exposure to drugs in utero, may lead to learning disability. Trauma of birth or trouble, Injury in the womb or after birth to neurological or central nervous system; Inheritance, lack of atmosphere for nursing, Weight of low birth, Medicines like cancer or childhood leukaemia, Premature birth & sensory impairments, including hearing loss or poor vision Nutritional deficits (Stanton, Chapman & Scott, 2001).

Reducing your child's risk of learning disabilities:

In fact, you cannot avoid some learning disorders, but there are strategies to minimize the odds of your child getting a disability Preventing, during and after your pregnancy, any alcohol, tobacco and recreational substances Preventing hazardous chemicals exposure during pregnancy and following the birth of your kid Assessing with your health care practitioner carefully danger against benefit to the medicine of your child, remove stressful influences from the home and social surroundings of your child, Obtain immediate assistance to rectify any sensory deficiencies, in particular hearing loss or impaired eyesight. Get early screenings for your kid and talk to your child's health care provider about early childhood development milestones, protect your kid by restricting drugs, both throughout pregnancy and during breastfeeding, provide your child with adequate nutrition and a healthy environment, and seek early help in cases where your child has a learning problem or a future disability (Vaughn & Fuchs, 2003).

Treating Learning Disabilities:

There are no cures for learning disabilities; however, early screening and intervention can help reduce or control many of them. If the underlying cause of the disability is corrected, the disability may disappear entirely over time. Special education services, including a team approach to developing the Individualized Education Program (I.E.P) and other medicines, will be the most effective therapy for child if they are diagnosed with learning disability if shown to be helpful. Occupational therapy and speech therapy are two examples of these services. Children's adaptation and progress can also be impacted by one-on-one tutoring with an experienced learning disability specialist (Silver, 1987).

Methodology

Research designs: In order to carry out this research, a quantitative study was used. Quantitative research is a data collection technique that answers questions about the current status of the subject in the study.

Population: This research study explores the prevalence of specific learning disabilities among primary school children, so the children studying in the primary schools of Punjab are the population of this study. For the purpose of study and generalization, group of element from which statistical sample is selected is termed as population (Siddique et al., 2021).

Sample: The sample was drawn based on simple random sampling. The data from 2392 children was collected studying in the primary schools of Punjab with the help of teachers. Small group of individuals which possess the properties and traits of the of population is called sample (Siddique et al., 2021).

Instrumentation: WIAT test was used to collect the data from the children. The tool was divided into seven parts to assess the prevalence of specific learning disabilities of children. These seven sections and the questions of each section are described in detail.

Oral language: In assessment of oral language of children the questions asked were What is your Name, what is Your Father Name, which alphabet comes after F, which alphabet comes before F, what is the Spelling of the word apple, tell me the story of Rabbit and Tortoise, what is the name of our prophet, and how many times do we offer prayer in a day.

Total Reading: In assessment of total reading of children the questions asked to read were I have a cat, my cat is white, it has a long tail, her eyes are brown, it likes milk, and I love to play with my cat.

Basic Reading: In assessment of basic reading of children the questions asked to read were Apple, Ball, Cat, Dog, Elephant and Frog.

Reading Comprehension and Fluency: In assessment of reading comprehension and Fluency of children the questions asked to read and comprehend were I have ___ Cats (1, 2, 3), My cat is ___ (White, Brown, Black), Cat has a ___ tail (Short, Long, No), Cat eyes are ___ (Black, Brown, White), Cat likes ___ (Milk, Butter, Bread), and I love to play with my ___ (Cat, Dog, Toys).

Written Expression: In assessment of written expression of children the questions asked to write were The Spelling of Apple, The Spelling of Elephant, Alphabets of English, Alphabets of Urdu, Counting from 1 to 50 and The Spelling of your name.

Mathematics: In assessment of mathematics of children the questions asked to calculate were Sum of 11 and 15, Difference of 11 and 15, Multiplication of 11 and 15, Table of 6, Counting from 1 to 100 and Division of 25 by 5.

Math Fluency: In assessment of math fluency of children the questions asked to calculate were What comes after 51, What comes before 124, What is 5×7 , Difference of $50 - 20$, Table of 10 and What is $25 + 25$.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection process was completed to judge the learning disabilities of students. A screening checklist was administered to take the observations of the students regarding their academic performance in the class. The data was sorted and interpreted to draw the results.

Table 1

Responses of the Students in Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III)

Sr#	Description	Correct (%)	Wrong (%)	Not Responded (%)	Score (%)
1	Oral Language	56.87	40.90	2.24	100
2	Total Reading	59.52	34.57	5.91	100
3	Basic Reading	51.46	40.97	7.56	100
4	Reading Comprehension and Fluency	34.57	59.52	5.91	100
5	Written Expression	49.23	44.69	6.08	100
6	Mathematics	49.94	46.38	3.68	100
7	Math Fluency	53.53	44.16	2.31	100
	Overall Achievement	50.73	44.46	4.81	100

Table 2

Oral Language.

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	OL-1	1774	74.16	578	24.16	40	1.67	2392	100
2	OL-2	1616	67.56	748	31.27	28	1.17	2392	100
3	OL-3	1316	55.02	1044	43.65	32	1.34	2392	100
4	OL-4	1434	59.95	934	39.05	24	1.00	2392	100
5	OL-5	868	36.29	1432	59.87	92	3.85	2392	100
6	OL-6	1302	54.43	978	40.89	112	4.68	2392	100
7	OL-7	1146	47.91	1202	50.25	44	1.84	2392	100
8	OL-8	1426	59.62	910	38.04	56	2.34	2392	100
	Total	10882	1774	74.16	578	24.16	40	1.67	2392

Table 2 shows that the numbers of students which were 1774 (74.2%), 1616 (67.6%), 1316 (55%), 1434 (59.6%), 868 (36.3%), 1302 (54.4%), 1146 (47%), 1426 (59.6%) responded correctly to the items OL-1, OL-2, OL-3, OL-4, OL-5, OL-6, OL-7, and OL-8 respectively.

Table 3

Total Reading.

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	TR-1	1028	42.98	1236	51.67	128	5.35	2392	100
2	TR-2	1556	65.05	684	28.60	152	6.35	2392	100
3	TR-3	2028	84.78	240	10.03	124	5.18	2392	100
4	TR-4	894	37.37	1398	58.44	100	4.18	2392	100
5	TR-5	1324	55.35	900	37.63	168	7.02	2392	100
6	TR-6	1712	71.57	504	21.07	176	7.36	2392	100
	Total	8542	59.52	4962	34.57	848	5.91	14352	100

Table 3 shows that the numbers of students which were 1028(42.97%), 1556(65.05%), 2028(84.78%), 894(37.37%), 1324(55.35%), 1712(71.57%) responded correctly to the items TR-1, TR-2, TR-3, TR-4, TR-5 and TR-6 respectively.

Table 4

Basic Reading

Sr.	Item	Correct	Wrong	Not Responded	Total
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No		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	BR-1	1248	52.17	912	38.13	232	9.70	2392	100
2	BR-2	1310	54.67	898	37.48	188	7.85	2396	100
3	BR-3	1068	44.65	1172	49.00	152	6.35	2392	100
4	BR-4	1022	42.73	1160	48.49	210	8.78	2392	100
5	BR-5	1712	71.57	504	21.07	176	7.36	2392	100
6	BR-6	1028	42.98	1236	51.67	128	5.35	2392	100
	Total	7388	51.46	5882	40.97	1086	7.56	14356	100

Table 4 shows that the numbers of students which were 1248(52.17%), 1310(54.76%), 1068(44.64%), 1022(42.72%), 1712(71.57%), 1028(42.97%) responded correctly to the items BR-1, BR-2, BR-3, BR-4, BR-5 and BR-6 respectively.

Table 5

Reading Comprehension and Fluency

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	RCF-1	1236	51.67	1028	42.98	128	5.35	2392	100
2	RCF-2	684	28.60	1556	65.05	152	6.35	2392	100
3	RCF-3	240	10.03	2028	84.78	124	5.18	2392	100
4	RCF-4	1398	58.44	894	37.37	100	4.18	2392	100
5	RCF-5	900	37.63	1324	55.35	168	7.02	2392	100
6	RCF-6	504	21.07	1712	71.57	176	7.36	2392	100
	Total	4962	34.57	8542	59.52	848	5.91	14352	100

Table 5 shows that the numbers of students which were 1236(51.7%), 684(28.6%), 240(10%), 1398(58.4%), 900(37.6%), 504(21.1%) responded correctly to the items RCF-1, RCF-2, RCF-3, RCF-4, RCF-5 and RCF-6 respectively.

Table 6

Written Expression

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	WE-1	1712	71.57	504	21.07	176	7.36	2392	100
2	WE-2	1028	42.98	1236	51.67	128	5.35	2392	100
3	WE-3	900	37.63	1324	55.35	168	7.02	2392	100
4	WE-4	504	21.07	1712	71.57	176	7.36	2392	100
5	WE-5	2028	84.78	240	10.03	124	5.18	2392	100
6	WE-6	894	37.37	1398	58.44	100	4.18	2392	100
	Total	7066	49.23	6414	44.69	872	6.08	14352	100

Table 6 shows that the numbers of students, which were 1712(71.57%), 1028(42.97%), 900(37.6%), 504(21.1%), 2028(84.78%), 894(37.37%), responded correctly to the items WE-1, WE-2, WE-3, WE-4, WE-5, and WE-6 respectively.

Table 7

Mathematics

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	M-1	1616	67.56	748	31.27	28	1.17	2392	100
2	M-2	1316	55.02	1044	43.65	32	1.34	2392	100
3	M-3	1434	59.95	934	39.05	24	1.00	2392	100
4	M-4	1398	58.44	894	37.37	100	4.18	2392	100
5	M-5	900	37.63	1324	55.35	168	7.02	2392	100

6	M-6	504	21.07	1712	71.57	176	7.36	2392	100
	Total	7168	49.94	6656	46.38	528	3.68	14352	100

Table 7 shows that the numbers of students, which were 1616(67.6%), 1316(55%), 1434(59.6%), 1398(58.4%), 900(37.6%), 504(21.1%), responded correctly to the items M-1, M-2, M-3, M-4, M-5 and M-6 respectively.

Table 8

Math Fluency

Sr. No	Item	Correct		Wrong		Not Responded		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	MF-1	1616	67.56	748	31.27	28	1.17	2392	100
2	MF-2	1316	55.02	1044	43.65	32	1.34	2392	100
3	MF-3	1434	59.95	934	39.05	24	1.00	2392	100
4	MF-4	868	36.29	1432	59.87	92	3.85	2392	100
5	MF-5	1302	54.43	978	40.89	112	4.68	2392	100
6	MF-6	1146	47.91	1202	50.25	44	1.84	2392	100
	Total	7682	53.53	6338	44.16	332	2.31	14352	100

Table 8 shows that the numbers of students which were 28(1.2%), 32(1.3%), 24(1%), 92(3.8%), 112(4.7%), 44(1.8%) responded correctly to the items MF-1, MF-2, MF-3, MF-4, MF-5 and MF-6 respectively.

Table 9

Comparison of Specific Learning Disability on the basis of Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III) among Gender (t-test).

Gender	N	Mean	df	t	Sig.
Male	1231	6.54	4172.46	-3.93	.06
Female	1161	6.03	2114		

*P > .05 Level of Significance

Table 9 indicates that the empirical information for male ($N=1231$, $M=6.54$) and for female ($N=1166$, $M=6.03$) with t-statistics ($t(4172.46) = -3.93$, $P > .05 = .06$) which leads to the decision that there is a significant difference in the prevalence of primary level students regarding the learning disabilities. Moreover, it reveals that males have facing more learning difficulties as compared to the female students.

Table 10

Comparison of Specific Learning Disability based on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III) among Living Area (t-test).

Living Area	N	Mean	df	t	Sig.
Rural	1149	7.01	2114	-1.40	.005
Urban	1243	6.69	2086		

*P < .05 Level of Significance

Table 10 indicates that the empirical information for rural ($N=1149$, $M=7.01$) and for urban ($N=1243$, $M=6.69$) with t-statistics ($t(2114) = -1.40$, $P < .05 = .005$) which leads to the decision that there is no significant difference in the prevalence of primary level students regarding the learning disabilities. Moreover, it reveals that urban students have facing more learning difficulties as compared to the rural students.

Findings and Conclusion

Data Analysis shows that the numbers of students, which were 1774, 1616, 1316, 1434, 868, 1302, 1146, and 1426 responded correctly to the items OL-1, OL-2, OL-3, OL-4, OL-5, OL-6, OL-7, and OL-8 respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III). The number of students, 1028, 1556, 2028, 894, 1324, and 1712 responded correctly to the items TR-1, TR-2, TR-3, TR-4, TR-5, and TR-6 respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III). The number of students, 1248, 1310, 1068, 1022, 1712, and 1028, responded correctly to the items BR-1, BR-2, BR-3, BR-4, BR-5, and BR-6 respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III). The number of students, 1236, 684, 240, 1398, 900, and 504, responded correctly to RCF-1, RCF-2, RCF-3, RCF-4, RCF-5, and RCF-6 respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III). The number of students, 1712, 1028, 900, 504, 2028, and 894, responded correctly to WE-1, WE-2, WE-3, WE-4, WE-5, and WE-6

respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III). The numbers of students, 1616, 1316, 1434, 1398, 900, and 504, responded correctly to the items M-1, M-2, M-3, M-4, M-5, and M-6 respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III). The numbers of students, which were 28, 32, 24, 92, 112, and 44, responded correctly to the items MF-1, MF-2, MF-3, MF-4, MF-5, and MF-6 respectively responses on Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III).

There may be a lack of proper curriculum behind those who have certain learning challenges in school that is not consistent with developmental phases of the children. It has to be enhanced in accordance with the stages of growth proposed by psychologists and research professionals. Poor teaching and educational processes are among the reasons why students' speech, writing, reading and mathematics might have specific difficulty of learning. Causes include main problems of the central nervous system which is working not properly. The main component of the instruction is the teacher's topic understanding, which is relatively inadequate at basic level in most institutions. Inferior understanding of the specific learning disability amongst students is prevalent for female teachings on primary level.

Discussion and Recommendations

There is no significant difference in the Comparison of Specific Learning Disability based on the Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III) among Gender. There is a substantial difference in the Comparison of Specific Learning Disability based on the Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III) among Living areas. The researchers conducted this experimental study to examine the effectiveness of the Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III) among the student of Specific Learning Disability and to ensure the content validity of the screening checklist of students with Specific learning difficulties in different fields of life such as difficulty in reading, writing, and Learning (Griffith, 2016). The opinion of a panel of experts in the relevant area was framed. For data analysis Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT-III) was used to determine the reliability of the screening checklist for students with Specific learning difficulties in school (Wissinger, & De La Paz, 2016). Following recommendations were made on the results and conclusions:

1. Further research is recommended at a macro level in line with this study at elementary, secondary, and higher secondary classes.
2. School teachers should use the designed diagnostic tool out the learning difficulties in different areas of Learning.
3. Ensure that educational policies and practices facilitate the inclusion of children with Specific Learning disabilities in mainstream schools. It may require changes in admission and management policies, school infrastructure, curriculum, evaluation, and assessment procedures.
4. Exceptional support services must be established to provide the necessary support.
5. Higher authorities should arrange in-service training for the management and teachers at their own schools for awareness.
6. Special advocacy and awareness campaigns should be launched to increase parents and other family members having children with Specific Learning disabilities.
7. Incentives for teachers and staff should be offered to work with children with Specific Learning disabilities.

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